

MCAA's vision for the next MFF: Strengthening European Competitiveness by empowering the MSCA

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MARIE CURIE ALUMNI ASSOCIATION

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About the Marie Curie Alumni Association

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network with 22,000+ members from over 150 countries, open to any past or present beneficiaries of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), not restricted to researchers, but including their supervisors and MSCA project managers. The MCAA aims to connect the MSCA community, supporting career development initiatives for MCAA members and advocating for research and researchers.

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Background

In light of the [European Commission's ongoing work towards shaping the post-2027 Multiannual Financial Framework \(MFF\)](#), the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) welcomes the possibility to provide input into the public consultation process. The Commission's ambition to create a focused, simpler, and more impactful EU budget, as outlined in [President von der Leyen's Political Guidelines](#), presents an important opportunity to ensure that the needs of the research and innovation community are well represented. Through this consultation, the MCAA aims to highlight key areas where EU funding can better support the advancement of scientific excellence, inclusivity, and the long-term sustainability of Europe's research ecosystem.

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The MCAA has responded to four public consultations related to the MFF, focusing on the following areas:

1. [EU's next long-term budget \(MFF\) — EU funding for competitiveness](#)
2. [EU's next long-term budget \(MFF\) — EU funding for external action](#)
3. [EU's next long-term budget \(MFF\) — EU funding for cross-border education, training and solidarity, youth, media, culture, and creative sectors, values, and civil society](#)
4. [EU's next long-term budget \(MFF\) — performance of the EU budget](#)

These consultations were based on the experiences of Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) fellows and developed with input from the MCAA Policy Working Group, the MCAA Board and the MCAA Secretariat.

The MCAA's response emphasises the critical need to significantly increase the budget for the next Framework Programme (FP10), proposing a **€220 billion budget** for research and innovation. This aligns with the goals set by the [Heitor report](#). Recent statements, like [the joint response by the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers \(Eurodoc\) and the MCAA on the Horizon Europe Interim Evaluation Report](#), [the Warsaw Declaration](#), [the European Parliament \(EP\) resolution](#), and [the joint statement by the European Research Council \(ERC\) and the European Innovation Council \(EIC\)](#), highlight these points. The MFF should underscore the call for a **standalone FP10** with an ambitious budget allocated solely to research and innovation. This funding must be ring-fenced within the post-2027 MMF to ensure

continued support for key programmes like the MSCA and the ERC, while safeguarding their **independence and impact**. The MCAA highlights the need for the MSCA and the ERC to be clearly independent and agile in their governance and operations, ensuring these programmes remain effective and impactful. The framework programme remains the cornerstone of Europe's research and innovation strategy.

Regarding EU external funding, the MCAA stresses the importance of strengthening the role of science in EU external action, particularly through science diplomacy and evidence-based approaches to counter disinformation. This includes supporting international scientific cooperation, building capacity in science communication and diplomacy, and enhancing trust in scientific expertise through citizen engagement, ultimately fostering stronger global partnerships and promoting informed decision-making.

The MCAA also advocates for robust EU funding to support cross-border education, training, and research mobility, notably through the MSCA. This supports global research collaborations and mobility, strengthening Europe's competitive edge, driving innovation, and addressing skills gaps, particularly in the digital and green sectors, which are essential for Europe's sustainable growth and a just transition. It ensures that communities, craftspeople, and small-scale producers are supported through targeted skill-building and included in innovation policy.

In terms of performance, the MCAA highlights the need for more realistic output indicators that provide qualitative and quantitative data on the real impact of projects. These indicators should be flexible and actionable to ensure reliability and ease of use. This aligns with the principles of the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#), which advocates for a more comprehensive and transparent approach to research evaluation. CoARA calls for broader types of outputs beyond traditional metrics, ensuring that performance indicators reflect meaningful, long-term outcomes, and fostering a more inclusive, fair, and transparent research assessment system across the EU.

Additionally, the MCAA calls for improved transparency in evaluating the performance of large entities under Pillar II of Horizon Europe, as their impact is often underreported compared to Pillar I programmes like the ERC and the MSCA.

Finally, the MCAA supports extending the requirement for a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) to all types of organisations involved in Horizon Europe projects. The GEP helps organisations assess their gender equity status and raise awareness of gender issues within research institutions. However, it is not yet mandatory for all organisations, and its inclusion across entities would ensure a more consistent approach to gender equality throughout the EU. Additionally, the MCAA welcomes the inclusion of the sex and gender dimension in Horizon Europe applications. While the gender criterion is already used to break ties in cases where projects score equally, the MCAA believes its impact would be greater if explicitly applied to project and work package leaders. This approach, recently adopted for Pillar II of Horizon Europe in 2025, is a positive step, and the MCAA expects it to enhance gender equality outcomes significantly.

The MCAA's response reflects the collective input of its members and aims to shape a more effective and inclusive future for EU research and innovation funding.

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